

Accelerated and Accurate Myocardial T₁ Mapping with PENGUIN: Combining Deep Learning with Extended Phase Graph Modeling

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Synopsis

Motivation: Myocardial τ_1 mapping sequences typically require multiple breath-hold scans, leading to limited spatial resolution, patient discomfort and motion artifacts. Moreover, mapping is generally accomplished through three-parameter exponential fitting, which may compromise the accuracy of the estimation due to the model's simplicity.

Goal(s): Improve τ_1 mapping estimation accuracy, while also reducing acquisition and reconstruction times.

Approach: We propose a physics-informed deep learning network to obtain myocardial τ_1 maps directly from undersampled k-space following the Extended Phase Graph formulation.

Results: Our method is able to estimate τ_1 maps for acceleration factors 4 and 8× with minimal error.

Impact: We propose a novel physics-based deep learning method that performs accelerated myocardial τ_1 mapping directly from undersampled kspace acquisitions considering the Extended Phase Graph formulation, greatly improving the accuracy of the estimated τ_1 values while shortening acquisition/reconstruction times.

Introduction

Model-based Deep Learning (DL) has become increasingly popular for accelerated MRI reconstruction and quantitative mapping. DL architectures that perform quantitative mapping directly from accelerated k-space have been proposed for τ_1 and τ_2 mapping in various anatomical regions¹⁻³. However, all of these approaches assume exponential recovery for τ_1 and τ_2 mapping, simplifying the relaxation dynamics. A more accurate way of modeling the signal is to consider the Extended Phase Graph (EPG) formulation; however, this can be very resource-consuming, especially in the⁴ case of cardiac τ_1 mapping, where simulated signals must consider the subjects' heart rate (HR). Here, we propose modifying our Phase Graph signal and Gradients QUantitative Inference machine (PENGUIN)⁵, initially proposed for brain T₂ mapping, to accelerate myocardial τ_1 mapping, whilst considering the EPG formulation. Compared to our previous implementation, this work has the following novelties: (a) quantitative mapping is now performed directly from undersampled k-space, instead of from reconstructed images; (b) signal intensity curves are now simulated not only for a range of τ_1 values, but also for a range of regular HR values, resulting in a comprehensive dictionary which moves the resource burden away from the inference stage and into the preprocessing stage.

Methods

PENGUIN combines a Recurrent Inference Machine⁶ with a dictionary of EPG simulated signal evolution curves that provides the network with a pre-calculated signal model, alleviating the computational burden during inference. In this work, PENGUIN aims to learn a *maximum a posteriori* estimator by unrolling the optimization process with a forward model given by:

$$d = UFE(T_I) + Noise$$

where d is the acquired (undersampled) k-space data, U is the undersampling operator, F is the Fourier Transform, and E is the EPG formulation that produces a signal intensity 4D image (3D image sampled at multiple inversion times) given a τ_1 value. PENGUIN performs $J=2$ inference steps to obtain J estimates of the τ_1 maps, which contribute to the loss function used to optimize the network:

$$L = \frac{1}{J+1} \sum_{j=0}^J 10^{-\frac{J-j+2}{J}} L_1(T_1, \hat{T}_1),$$

where L_1 is the L1-norm loss, evaluated in the myocardium. PENGUIN follows the architecture in *Figure 1*. Networks were trained in an NVIDIA Quadro RTX 8000 GPU, ADAM optimizer, learning rate=1e-4, 300 epochs, considering $C=64$ and $C=256$ channels for acceleration factors 4 and 8, respectively.

Data were obtained from MICCAI's 2023 CMR reconstruction challenge⁷. τ_1 mapping was conducted following a MOLLI sequence which acquired 9 images (4-(1)-3-(1)-2), short axis (SA) view only, FOV=360×307 mm², spatial resolution=1.4×1.4 mm, slice thickness=5.0 mm, TR=2.67 ms, TE=1.13 ms, partial Fourier=7/8, and GRAPPA factor =2, on a 3T MAGNETOM Vida Siemens scanner. We considered only the single coil, fully-sampled dataset and slices 1-4; subjects #001-#100 were used for training, #101-#110 for validation, and #111-#120 for testing. K-space data were undersampled retrospectively, following a radial k-t sampling trajectory with golden angle increments.

EPG-based simulations were implemented for the protocol described above, HR sampled from 28 to 102 bpm, $\tau_1=0:1:2000$ ms, $\tau_2=50$ ms and used to build a dictionary of complex τ_1 -weighted signal intensity curves for varying HRs. Ground-truth τ_1 maps (GT) were obtained by performing a pattern recognition approach over the reconstructed, fully sampled signal intensity images, through dot product matching. In addition, we also performed a three-parameter exponential fitting⁸ over the reconstructed images to illustrate the differences between exponential and EPG-based estimation.

Zero-filled (ZF) and Compressed Sensing (CS) reconstructions were performed to compare with PENGUIN. The CS approach consisted in a wavelet-based CS algorithm to reconstruct the images. The pattern recognition approach described above was employed to obtain the corresponding ZF and CS τ_1 maps. Maps were evaluated through the relative error and the mean structural similarity index measurement (MSSIM) with respect to the GT values.

Results

Figures 2 and 3 illustrate the estimated maps with ZF, CS and PENGUIN for distinct test subjects, slices, and acceleration factors. τ_1 maps estimated with PENGUIN achieved mean relative errors of $10.1 \pm 11.0\%$ and

15.9±15.4%, and mean MSSIM scores of 0.999±0.001 and 0.998±0.001, for accelerations 4 and 8×, respectively (*Figure 4*). *Figure 5* depicts the AHA segmentation analysis on all estimated τ_1 maps. PENGUIN requires only 1.49s and 0.41Gb of RAM to infer a τ_1 map.

Conclusions & Discussion

We successfully modified PENGUIN to perform myocardial τ_1 mapping directly from undersampled k-space with improved accuracy when compared to three-parameter exponential-based fitting. Moreover, PENGUIN is less resource-consuming than CS-based inference, since the computational burden is moved to the preprocessing stage. In the future, we will incorporate sensitivity information from multiple coils (parallel imaging) into the signal model to allow larger acceleration rates, and build the dictionaries considering an additional range of τ_2 values for increased accuracy.

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Figures

Fig 1. PENGUIN architecture drawn for inference step j . At each inference step, the estimate of the τ_1 maps p_j^λ is given to the dictionary to obtain the signal-intensity and corresponding derivative attributed to each τ_1 value in the map. With these, the gradient of the negative log-likelihood of the model ∇_{L_j} is calculated, concatenated to p_j^λ and given as input to the network, which outputs the incremental update to the estimated maps.

The network uses two memory vectors h_j to learn the optimization process.

Fig 2. τ_1 maps estimated with the different methods applied to 5 distinct test subjects (rows), with different HRs and acceleration factor $4\times$; from left to right: ground-truth (GT), Exponential Fitting, zero-filled (ZF), compressed-sensing (CS), and PENGUIN. The different slices are shown in each frame of the animation.

Fig 3. Ground-truth (GT) and estimated τ_1 maps with zero-lled (ZF), compressed-sensing (CS) and PENGUIN methods for 1 representative subject, HR=64 bpm, for acceleration factors 4 (top) and 8 \times (bottom).

Fig 4. Violin plots of the (a) T1 relative errors and (b) MSSIM scores obtained with zero-lled (ZF), compressed-sensing (CS) and PENGUIN, for acceleration factors 4 and 8 \times . A two-factor ANOVA and pairwise-test was carried out to identify statistically significant differences between methods, indicated by * (p-value<0.05) and *** (p-value<0.001).

Fig 5. Segmental distribution of (a) mean τ_1 values and (b) standard deviation according to the AHA 16-segment model, for 2 representative subjects and acceleration $4\times$. PENGUIN provides results that are in good agreement with the ground-truth (GT) τ_1 values, despite the lower variation within each segment.

